

IMT Mines Alès
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Manufacturing fiber reinforced recycled Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) TAPES: a capillarity-based approach

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CONTEXT

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Major environmental issues :

- One of the most widely used polymers ¹ → **413 Mt of plastic produced in 2023** ² → **6,2 % of PET waste** ²
- Efficient, sustainable, circular and low-energy impact recycling method are **essential**

Current recycling method :

- Most plastics are **shredded**: mechanical recycling process → **degradation of mechanical properties** ³
- New recycling method: impregnation of fibers to make thermoplastic tapes → **Capillarity characterization**

GOALS

- Circular
- Sustainable
- Low energy impact

METHODOLOGY

3 important steps :

- **Dissolution** of PET with a suitable solvent
- **Impregnation** of the solution on/ in the fibers
- **Precipitation** of the polymer on/in the fibers thank to a non-solvent

METHODOLOGY - DISSOLUTION

Théorème de solubilité de Hansen ⁴

$$\delta = \sqrt{\delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2 + \delta_h^2}$$

Hexafluoroisopropanol
(HFIP)

PET flakes
1-2 cm²

HFIP, 25°C, without
agitating

HFIP/PET solution
Limit : 30 wt.%

METHODOLOGY - PRECIPITATION

NIPS : Non-solvent Induced Phase Separation ⁵

Non-solvent : Ethanol
Solvent : HFIP

- Methods from **membranes fabrication principles**
- **Ethanol** as a **non-solvent**
- **Diffusion** of the solvent in the non-solvent and of the non-solvent on the solvent

CHARACTERIZATION - PET

Several analyses shows that PET properties are conserved ⁶

IMPREGNATION - CHARACTERIZATION

Characterization of impregnation kinetics

Capillary wicking ⁷

$$m^2(t) = C \times \frac{\rho^2 \gamma_L \cos \theta_a}{\eta} t$$

Density

Viscosity

Surface Tension

HFIP pur

5 wt.% PET

10 wt.% PET

15 wt.% PET

IMPREGNATION - CHARACTERIZATION

Density determination

$$\rho = V \times m$$

IMPREGNATION - CHARACTERIZATION

Viscosity determination ⁸

$$\eta = \frac{M}{2\pi R^3 \Omega}$$

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IMPREGNATION - CHARACTERIZATION

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IMPREGNATION - CHARACTERIZATION

Surface tension determination ⁹

$$F_c = mg = \gamma_{LV} p \cos\theta$$

$$\gamma_{LV} = \frac{mg}{p}$$

IMPREGNATION – WICKING TESTS

Determination of impregnation kinetics as a function of concentration of PET

$$m^2(t) = \left[\frac{(c\bar{r})\epsilon^2(\pi R^2)^2}{2} \right] \times \frac{\rho^2 \gamma_L \cos\theta_a}{\eta} t$$

$L = 20 \text{ mm}$
 $R = \varnothing/2 = 1,75 \text{ mm}$
 $c\bar{r} = 6,44 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mm}$
 $V_f = 51,51 \%$

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PET	$m^2/t \text{ (g}^2/\text{s)}$	R^2	$\theta_a \text{ (}^\circ\text{)}$
5 wt%	1,554E-05	0,991	88,1
10 wt%	1,471E-05	0,993	81,6
15 wt%	4,217E-06	0,993	81,3

IMPREGNATION LINE – METHODOLOGY

MODULES OF IMPREGNATION LINE

- Impregnation bath : polymer solution
- Precipitation bath : non-solvent
- Guide rollers
- Steamrollers
- Motorised winding coil

Parameters optimization

- **Impregnation** : impregnation speed, rollers tension, concentration of polymer
- **Precipitation** : precipitation speed, solvent recovery
- **Tapes characterization** : Morphology and porosity characterization, mechanical behaviour, fibres volumic fraction

IMPREGNATION LINE – METHODOLOGY

MODULES OF IMPREGNATION LINE

IMPREGNATION LINE – CHARACTERIZATION

SEM analyses – Morphology of the thermoplastic tapes

- Carbon fibers **IM7 12k** - Hexcel
- $V = 6\text{mm/s}$

CONCLUSIONS PROSPECTS

CONCLUSIONS

- **Dissolution / Precipitation method** has been selected and validated.
- **Innovative and efficient method for recycling PET** has been developed.
- **Production of tapes** has started and is running successfully

PROSPECTS

- **Optimise** production parameters : speed, tension, concentration
- **Characterization** of the produced tapes
- Test with a **robotised draping process**

Thank you for your attention

